

Considering Discussion Types to Support Collective Sensemaking During a Storyline Unit

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Abstract:

A key goal of recent reforms in science education has been to support students' collective sensemaking, in which they work together to understand a natural phenomenon. This work is often done during class discussions, but facilitating those discussions is challenging. In this study, we used a framework of three discussion types to investigate how classroom discussions differ throughout a storyline curricular unit: *initial ideas* discussions aim to surface students' ideas about a phenomenon; *building understandings* discussions aim to construct claims based on an investigation or data; and *consensus* discussions aim to bring together multiple claims over time to explain a phenomenon or event. We used this framework to analyze the idea work and turns taken in classroom discussions from one highly skilled middle school teacher. This analysis resulted in three takeaways. First, we found the teacher consistently worked to surface and clarify his students' ideas. This is as an important step in collective sensemaking that comes before the construction and critique of those ideas and can support a sense of belonging for students who typically do not identify with science. Second, we characterized a distinct talk pattern closely associated with surfacing and clarifying ideas across all three discussion types: the Propose-Probe-Clarify-Restate (PPCR) sequence. PPCR is distinct from previously identified talk patterns in the teacher's use of clarifying and restating to honor the ideas students bring to a discussion and to restate them to ensure they are accepted into a public record. Finally, we found that each discussion type required a distinct set of teacher moves to achieve its goal. Surfacing and clarifying ideas is necessary but insufficient to support collective sensemaking. Therefore, different talk moves, such as asking for evidence and evaluating claims for their connection to the phenomenon of interest, are required in building understandings and consensus discussions.

Keywords: sensemaking, classroom discussion, curriculum, storyline

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Recent work in science education has stressed the importance of supporting students as they make sense of the natural world around them, rather than simply learn facts (Schwarz et al., 2017). As they engage in this sensemaking work, students individually and collectively craft causal explanations of phenomena, deepening their understanding of both the phenomenon of interest and how scientists come to learn things about the universe (National Research Council, 2012; Osborne & Patterson, 2011; Zembal-Saul & Hershberger, 2020). A focus on supporting student sensemaking rather than simple memorization and repetition of information is also important because it values the diverse array of experiences and cognitive resources students bring to science class and therefore can create a more just and equitable learning environment (Davis et al., 2020; Rosebery et al., 2010).

One of the key ways to support this collective sensemaking is through classroom discourse that encourages students to figure out ideas based on evidence collected in class (Lemke, 1990; Michaels & O'Connor, 2017; Zangori & Pinnow, 2020). Classroom talk is well-researched and much is known about how to support students in engaging in the discourse of science (Park et al., 2017). What can be overlooked in the classroom discourse literature, however, is the idea that the type of intellectual work the class must engage in changes over time, and therefore the talk that supports that work must also change. For example, when students are first exposed to a phenomenon, the necessary sensemaking work involves considering the phenomenon, identifying any gaps in their understanding, and motivating the need for future investigations (Phillips et al., 2018). This work is very different from what happens after students finish a series of investigations and need to consider how the evidence collected across those investigations supports (or does not support) their explanation of the

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phenomenon of interest (Harris et al., 2012). Given these changing goals across a curricular unit, it stands to reason that forms of classroom discourse must also change over time.

We know that the teacher plays a central role in the facilitation of student talk and therefore sensemaking (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2019). This facilitation is particularly important because the moves that teachers make can support students in making their thinking visible to others, deepening their own thinking, and taking up and working with each other's ideas (Kawalkar & Vijapurkar, 2013; Kloser et al., 2019; O'Connor & Michaels, 2019). Most work in the field, however, has considered discussion in general (e.g. Michaels & O'Connor, 2012) or focused on a particular kind of discussion, such as evidence building conversations after an investigation (e.g. Manz & Renga, 2017).

As we look across discussions in a unit, however, we would expect the particular roles and moves a teacher might use to shift in relation to the shifting goals of the classroom discourse. A discussion that focuses on students hearing and establishing their own initial ideas would require different interactional and epistemic supports than one focused on students coming to an agreement about how a particular investigation furthers their understanding of a phenomenon. The teacher plays a central role in coordinating these discussions to achieve their goals, but little is known about how teachers manage those shifting goals and moves over the course of a unit.

Therefore, in this study we investigated the implementation of class-wide discussions in a type of reform-based curriculum called a storyline curriculum to elucidate the moves the teacher made during those discussions, how they supported students' collective sensemaking, and how they varied or stayed constant over the course of multiple discussions with different goals. To do this work, we asked the following research questions: (1) How does idea work vary across three class-wide discussions with different instructional goals? (2) How do interactional patterns vary

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across these same discussions? and (3) To what degree and how did the teacher moves shape the collective sensemaking done during these discussions?

Background

In this study, we used three major constructs to guide our investigation: collective sensemaking, classroom discourse, and teacher moves to support both. Here, we define what we mean by each of these constructs and how they have already been studied and discussed in the literature. One kind of curriculum that has recently emerged to support students in sensemaking through classroom discourse is storyline curricula (Reiser et al., 2017). We end this section by describing what storyline curricula are and what we currently know about how they support student sensemaking.

Collective Sensemaking in Science Learning

A focus on students' sensemaking has become popular in science education research recently, even though there is not yet a consistent application of the term in the literature (Odden & Russ, 2019). In their review of sensemaking research, Odden and Russ identified three different strands of sensemaking research: sensemaking as a stance towards learning, sensemaking as a cognitive process, and sensemaking as a discursive practice. All three strands attend to the individual student's thinking, but we find the third strand particularly powerful because it also explicitly addresses the way that sensemaking happens collectively between people. Sensemaking as a discursive practice highlights the way that communication supports sensemaking, especially as students make, critique, and revise claims about the natural world (Berland & Reiser, 2009; Odden & Russ, 2019).

Ford (2012) made a key contribution to this strand of sensemaking research by analyzing the work done by scientists and science learners. He identified two competing but interconnected

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activities in dialogic sensemaking: construction and critique. He defined construction as the act of building ideas about a phenomenon through the coordination of multiple pieces of evidence. He defined critique as checking the explanation that had been constructed by yourself or others to make sure all of the pieces of evidence are coherent and that the explanation holds together. Ford argues that just as scientists make sense of the world by moving back and forth between construction and critique of ideas, so should science students as they collectively work together.

In looking at sensemaking in the classroom for this study, therefore, we adopted Odden and Russ's definition of sensemaking as "a dynamic process of building or revising an explanation in order to 'figure something out'" (2019, pp. 191–192). In addition, we paid particular attention to the ways in which sensemaking took place through the navigation between construction and critique of ideas as part of a collective, dialogic process (Ford, 2012).

Given this definition of sensemaking, we can see multiple examples of how supporting student sensemaking leads to stronger student understanding, more effective use of the practices of scientists, and an expanded understanding of what science is and who can do it. For example, Brown and Ryoo (2008) demonstrated the benefits of separating scientific language from science concepts and allowing students to build conceptual understanding using their own language before adding scientific vocabulary. They used a quasi-experimental method to show that students given an opportunity to make sense of science ideas with their own language showed stronger improvement on assessments than those taught with vocabulary-first methods. Bismack and Haefner (2020) further developed these ideas in a case study of a highly skilled first grade teacher, illustrating how a focus on student sensemaking helped students to engage in science practices and develop complex understanding of scientific ideas.

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In addition to the benefits of sensemaking on students' conceptual understanding, it also has the potential to open up science for students not traditionally represented in the discipline. Allowing students to build explanations of phenomena they have experienced can “desettle” expectations about what science is and who gets to practice it (Bang et al., 2012). This desettling can be done by recognizing and celebrating the intellectual resources and experiences students bring to their sensemaking, pushing both teachers and students to expand their perception of who can “do science” (Bang et al., 2017; Davis et al., 2020). Valuing students' wide array of experiences, thoughts, and questions can expand their vision of who gets to do science, and some have argued that heterogeneity is in fact *fundamental* for learning (Rosebery et al., 2010).

Discussion in Science Classrooms

Collective sensemaking requires social interaction, and the most frequent mode for this interaction in science classrooms is the classroom discussion, in which students should engage in the language of science (Lemke, 1990). The nature of classroom discussion is complex, however, and much work has been done to analyze various types of classroom talk. Mortimer and Scott (2003) proposed two dimensions for analyzing classroom talk: the degree of interactivity and the positioning of multiple ideas during the talk. Within this framework, classroom communication can range from *interactive*, where that talk invites the contribution of others, to *noninteractive*, in which the talk excludes others from participation. Simultaneously, communication can range from *authoritarian*, in which one idea is valued, to *dialogic*, in which multiple ideas are positioned as equally valuable. Any given form of communication, therefore, would lie at the intersection of these two dimensions. For example, the well-known Initiation-Response-Evaluation form of discourse (IRE; Mehan, 1979) is interactive and authoritarian because it

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welcomes another's participation but for the purpose of consolidating towards one accepted idea (Mortimer & Scott, 2003; Scott et al., 2006).

This biaxial analysis of talk patterns, which we have summarized in Figure 1, helps to identify the prerequisites for talk that supports collective sensemaking. Multiple ideas must be presented and valued, meaning the talk must be dialogic, and multiple speakers must participate, making it interactive. If talk is not interactive and dialogic, then it cannot support collective sensemaking (Scott et al., 2006). Nevertheless, simply being interactive and dialogic is insufficient, because it is possible for a range of ideas to be presented and valued by multiple people but not actually put in conversation with each other.

Therefore, within dialogic, interactive talk, we must also attend to the degree that ideas are *interanimated*, or related and connected to each other (Bakhtin, 1981; Scott et al., 2006). In situations in which there is low interanimation of ideas, students may successively list their ideas but little work is done to connect or compare them, which limits the critiquing activity key to scientific sensemaking (Ford, 2012). It is therefore only when talk is dialogic, interactive, *and* with highly interanimated ideas that we are likely to see students engaging in the kinds of collective sensemaking that truly supports development of complex understandings of scientific ideas and practices.

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Figure 1*Examples of Classroom Talk Placed Along Dialogic and Interactive Axes*

Although the goal of collective sensemaking has been accepted for quite a while, multiple studies over time continue to show that IRE and other similar closed, teacher-centered discourse forms remain the most common in science classrooms (e.g. Nassaji & Wells, 2000; Pimentel & McNeill, 2013; Rees & Roth, 2019; Scott et al., 2006; Wells & Mejia Arauz, 2006).

Nevertheless, researchers have observed and characterized other discussion patterns in science classrooms. For example, Mortimer and Scott (2003) described the I-R-F-R-F- pattern, in which there are repeated rounds of student response (R) and teacher feedback or questions (F). This pattern can either be a repeated sequence with one student or a more interactive sequence in which multiple different students respond to the teachers' feedback (Mortimer & Scott, 2003). Similarly, Rees and Roth (2019) characterized the I-R-Q-R-A form of classroom discourse, in which the teacher initiates a conversation (I), a student responds (R), and the teacher and student(s) proceed through rounds of clarifying questions (Q), responses, and non-evaluative acknowledgement of the responses (A). Taken together, these studies show that classroom talk

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can be much more complex than the well-known IRE structure. This complexity opens up questions about what role the teacher might play in facilitating sensemaking talk that supports these more complex forms.

The Role of the Teacher in Facilitating Sensemaking through Discussion

Much of the research on classroom discourse is predicated on the idea that the teacher plays a central role in facilitating the talk, influencing the degree to which students actually engage in sensemaking around a natural phenomenon (Kelly, 2014; National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2019). One tool that teachers can use to support discourse that is dialogic and interanimates ideas are talk moves. Talk moves are “roughly utterance-sized units of talk, intended (as a ‘move’ in a game) to get the other player(s) to respond in some way” (O’Connor & Michaels, 2019, p. 168). These moves, such as asking a speaker to say more or asking one student to summarize what another has said, can be used to achieve important goals for discourse that supports collective sensemaking, including deepening individual students’ thinking and positioning students to engage with each other’s ideas (Michaels & O’Connor, 2015). Kloser and colleagues (2019) used talk moves as part of their methods classes for pre-service teachers and found that as pre-service teachers rehearsed with the moves, they brought them into their practice to mostly strong effect. This work demonstrated that talk moves can be taken up by teachers and used effectively in the classroom to support student sensemaking.

Some have also shifted from general talk moves to support students’ sensemaking to identifying moves specific for particular kinds of discussions or scientific practices. For example, Manz and Renga (2017) studied how teachers supported students in constructing evidence from investigations and highlighted ways that teachers can direct questions, promote disagreement, or provide information to guide and shape the work done in those discussions. Alternatively,

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Kawalkar and Vijapurkar (2013) looked specifically at the kinds of questions teachers ask when using inquiry or traditional methods of instruction and demonstrated that teachers supporting inquiry used a higher variety of question types, positioning students to generate, prove, and refine ideas over time. Their study showed how teachers' moves change over the course of multiple lessons but left open the question of how teachers might know when to shift their questioning strategies and what goals or ideas might be guiding that shift.

One of the proposed answers to this question has been to look at teachers' goals for a particular discussion or discourse situation. For example, McNeill and Pimentel (2010) studied discourse during the same lesson on climate change in three different teachers' classrooms and found that the degree of student-student talk and interanimation of ideas varied greatly between teachers. One of the reasons for this variation was the teachers' perceived goals of the discussion; the teacher who believed the goal was to have his students provide evidence for climate change facilitated a more non-interactive discussion than the one who aimed to have her students hear and respond to each other's ideas. Similarly, Rees and Roth (2017) identified three talk situations during classroom science investigations that each had a different goal (e.g. to share results or to solve a problem). They found that each situation had its own characteristic talk pattern that ranged from the traditional IRE structure to more complex forms involving multiple students contributing and responding to each other. The pattern across these studies is the importance of understanding the goals of a discussion in order to choose appropriate talk moves to support collective sensemaking in that particular situation.

Storyline Curricula

One recent innovation in curricular design to address the connection between sensemaking and discourse as well as the difficulties teachers have with implementing both is the

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design of storyline curricula (Reiser et al., 2017, in press). In storyline curricula, units are based around an anchoring phenomenon about which students ask questions to motivate their investigations (Windschitl et al., 2018). Students work together to determine which questions they find most interesting, which investigations to do, how those investigations help them to understand the anchoring phenomenon, and what further investigations are necessary (Zivic et al., 2018). The curricular materials are written to anticipate the questions students are likely to pose. In order to get a sense of what students might ask about particular phenomena, part of the design process for storyline units is to pilot them with students who provide feedback both in terms of how interesting each phenomenon is and what questions it brings up for them (Edelson et al., in press; Reiser et al., in press).

Given the relative novelty of storyline curricula, not much research has been done on their impacts on student sensemaking. Nevertheless, some work has shown that the storyline approach can have positive effects on class participation across gender, racial, and ethnic groups (Krumm et al., 2020). In addition, whole class discussions in storyline units have been shown to position students as legitimate participants who work together to understand scientific phenomena (Zangori & Pinnow, 2020). Nevertheless, in that same study Zangori and Pinnow also found that not every discussion achieved these positive outcomes, highlighting again the need to understand how we can support teachers who use these materials to consistently engage students in discussions that support collective sensemaking.

The Discussion Types Framework

Although one goal for science classrooms is to support collective sensemaking, the nature of that sensemaking will not be uniform throughout a curricular unit. Because the sensemaking work changes over the course of a unit, the discussions that a teacher facilitates to support that

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work must also change. Some discussions will have goals such as eliciting students' ideas while others may focus more on building an idea from a particular investigation or connecting multiple investigations together to explain a phenomenon. Some work has been done on outlining purposes of discussion (e.g. Michaels & O'Connor, 2012), considering discussions based on the kinds of construction and/or critique of ideas that should take place (Ford, 2012), and defining talk situations that elicit characteristic complex discourse patterns (Rees & Roth, 2017).

Unfortunately, there is not a consistent agreement in the literature about the possible goals for discussions. To address this issue, we build on previous research focused on discussion types in science (Michaels & Moon, 2016; Windschitl et al., 2018) to outline a framework of three discussion types that might take place in a storyline unit, each of which has a distinct instructional and epistemic goal. Those types are: *initial ideas*, *building understandings*, and *consensus* discussions (see Table 1).

Table 1

Goals of Three Discussion Types

Discussion Type	Main Goals
Initial ideas	Students share experiences and ideas related to a phenomenon
Building understandings	Students construct claims based on evidence from an investigation or secondary data source
Consensus	Students connect multiple claims together from across lessons to come to agreement about an explanation of a phenomenon

Initial ideas discussions serve the purpose of getting students' initial ideas and experiences on the table. As a result, these discussions must provide students with the opportunity to share draft ideas and to realize that there are gaps in their collective understanding. In turn, these gaps promote curiosity and motivate what the class could do next to

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figure out the phenomenon of interest. This type of discussion often occurs near the beginning of a unit or shortly after introducing an anchoring phenomenon (Windschitl et al., 2018). These discussions are particularly important for establishing a joint need for investigation among the classroom community (Reiser et al., in press; Zivic et al., 2018).

Building understandings discussions ask students to share claims and reasoning based on evidence. They often take place after students have conducted an investigation and collected their own data or analyzed second-hand data. These discussions also involve students connecting, critiquing, and building on each other's ideas. As a result, they typically conclude with the class using evidence to arrive at tentative conclusions about a specific lesson question.

The goal of consensus discussions is that the entire class come to agreement on some important idea that they have been working on over the period of multiple lessons, often related to the anchoring phenomenon (Windschitl et al., 2018). During these discussions, students are asked to put together multiple ideas built from experiences they have had over time to come to an agreement on what they do and do not yet know about the phenomenon. In order to meet these goals, these conversations typically include proposing ideas about which the class might come to consensus and then evaluating or discussing them to decide if the class agrees.

Given that the instructional purpose of and the necessary idea work for each of these discussions is different, it stands to reason that the kinds of sensemaking required of students, and therefore the implementation moves the teacher must make, may be different. In this study, therefore, we used this framework to guide our analysis of discussions across the unit to determine how teacher moves changed (or did not change) depending on the type of discussion.

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Methods

We used a single case study approach in order to capture the particularity and complexity of a single case (Patton, 2002). A case study is suitable where the focus of the study is answering “how” and “why” questions about contemporary phenomena and generating initial theory-building insights (Yin, 2018). Our single instrumental case study focused on how one classroom community enacted one class-wide discussion of each type. We considered this an instrumental case study because the goal of this work was to address and understand a specific issue (Stake, 2005; Yin, 2018): how idea work, interactional patterns, and teacher moves varied across one classroom community’s enactment of different discussion types. By doing this work, we hoped to establish initial connections between productive forms of idea work and interaction patterns to support collective sensemaking in each discussion type.

Curricular Context

This study focused on one teacher’s pilot of a middle school science unit on metabolic reactions in the human body. The curriculum came from OpenSciEd, a project focused on developing high-quality, open-source curriculum and professional development materials. OpenSciEd writes storyline curricula and uses the discussion types framework we have outlined to define and categorize the whole group discussions in the unit (OpenSciEd, 2019b). This study focused on implementation of the pilot version of the Metabolic Reactions unit (OpenSciEd, 2019a). The unit uses the case of M’Kenna as its anchoring phenomenon. M’Kenna, a thirteen-year-old girl, was suffering from a range of unexplained symptoms such as weight loss, lethargy, and headaches, and students were initially presented with her complaints and a note from her visit to the doctor. This anchoring phenomenon was used to encourage students to ask questions such as “what does her digestive system look like and how does it compare to a healthy

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person's?" or "why does she lose weight with regular meals?" These questions motivated investigations that were designed to help students figure out how healthy body systems work together in an effort to explain what was happening in M'Kenna's body.

Participants

The teacher, whom we call Mr. Morse, taught in a major city in the Northeastern United States. We purposely selected (Merriam, 1998) Mr. Morse because he was an award-winning instructor with more than 20 years of middle school science teaching experience. In addition, because of his strong enactment of the curriculum materials, he participated in the production of the OpenSciEd professional development resources. Therefore, we expected he might provide a compelling image of how storyline discussions could be successfully enacted to support collective sensemaking. Further, studying his practice offered the opportunity to identify and characterize powerful examples of when even a veteran teacher struggled to facilitate this sensemaking. Therefore, given Mr. Morse's substantial teaching experience and capacity, we argue that he was an ideal choice for this single instrumental case study of discussion types. Once we selected him, we obtained consent from Mr. Morse, his students, and their parents or guardians to record their classroom interactions.

Mr. Morse taught in a highly rated, public, magnet school in an urban district. During the year of data collection, his school enrolled 1,562 students in grades 7-12 and had a student-teacher ratio of 17 to 1. The student body had 47% of students on free or reduced lunch, 90% students of color, 3% were classified as English language learners, and 4% were classified as having a disability. According to state test scores, 94% of students were at least proficient in math and 98% in reading. The school's academic program specialized in science, technology, engineering and mathematics. We focused on one of Mr. Morse's 8th grade classes. The class

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had 31 students and matched the demographics and academic achievement of the school as a whole.

Data Collection

While Mr. Morse was implementing the pilot version of the Metabolic Reactions unit during the fall of 2018, the third author went into his classroom approximately once a week to observe and video-record. Each session involved recording the entire 60-minute period. During whole-group time the camera and microphone were positioned to capture as many students as possible. When small groups were working, the camera was aimed at one group to capture the students' talk. It took Mr. Morse approximately two months to complete the entire unit, which resulted in recording 12 different class sessions.

After Mr. Morse completed the unit, we reviewed the entire set of recordings and identified any whole-group discussions that represented one of the three discussion types. We selected recordings from three lessons, one for each type. These were selected based on being substantial enough in length to allow the class to engage interactively in idea work. Furthermore, each example clearly included key characteristics of that discussion type (e.g. consensus discussions should draw from multiple lessons). The three discussions we focus on for this study are summarized in Table 2.

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Table 2*Description of Focal Discussions*

Discussion Type	Discussion Description	Lesson
Initial ideas	Students develop initial ideas for investigating M’Kenna’s medical condition and make decisions about where to head in the next lesson.	Lesson 1
Building understandings	Students discuss the data from two investigations where they trapped the gases produced by burning food in order to confirm that food undergoes a chemical reaction in the body.	Lesson 11
Consensus	Students review the ideas they have figured out so far in lessons 1-6 and discuss how these ideas might help them to answer their questions about M’Kenna.	Lesson 7

Data Analysis

We analyzed the focal discussion using two different lenses. First, we used a turn-taking lens. In this interactive analysis, we documented whether the teacher or the students were speaking in each turn during discussion enactment. Second, we used an idea work lens. In this epistemic analysis, we determined the epistemic function of each utterance spoken during collective sensemaking in each discussion. We then analyzed the patterns of epistemic functions instantiated in broader conversational segments (Robertson et al., 2015) in and across each discussion. In order to complete both analyses, we transcribed each discussion in full.

Turn-Taking Analysis

Analytic framing. Drawing on conversation analysis (CA; Schegloff & Sacks, 1973), we conceptualized the discussions as accomplished through turns-at-talk in interaction. Our turn-taking analysis focused on the construction of turns (Schegloff, 2007) by the teacher and students in each discussion enactment. In focusing on turn-talking, we were able to discern the distinctive and recurrent pattern of interactions implemented during collective sensemaking in each

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discussion. These patterns of interaction structure the forms of epistemic activity made relevant through the teacher and students turns-at-talk (Schegloff, 2007).

Analytic flow. We first coded each turn based on whether a student or the teacher was speaking. We completed this initial coding for each of the three discussion enactments. During the consensus discussion, Mr. Morse employed a student facilitator who had a distinct role from the other students, so we added a third code for that discussion to distinguish the student facilitator from other students. This code enabled us to avoid collapsing the student facilitator into the larger student population and therefore more accurately capture the interaction patterns for the discussion. We then tabulated the percentage of turns taken by the teacher, the students, and the student-facilitator in each discussion. We also compiled counts of the different patterns of interaction in each discussion. These patterns involved sequences of turn-taking where the teacher would initiate interaction and one or more students would subsequently respond. We classified whether the pattern of interaction involved a teacher-student dyad (i.e. TS) or chain of student responses to the teacher's initial contribution (i.e. TSS, TSSS, TSSSS, etc.). Together, these analyses allowed us to identify the recurrent patterns of interaction across each discussion. In turn, we mobilized these recurrent patterns to construct an interactive theme related to the classroom community's collective sensemaking in each discussion.

Idea Work Analysis

Analytic framing. Our idea work analysis took a deductive approach to the discussions, assuming that by analyzing individual parts of the discussion, we could make discoveries about how ideas were used in the discussions overall (Erickson, 2006). We enacted this approach by documenting the individual epistemic functions of classroom utterances in the discussion in order to make broader generalizations about the idea work being done in each discussion. In this

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analysis, we defined an utterance as a unit of talk with a distinct function (Hanks, 1996) and the epistemic function as the way an utterance proposed or worked with an idea. For example, if a speaker asks for or repeats a previously stated idea, we coded that epistemic function as “restating an idea.”

We used interaction analysis (IA) (Jordan & Henderson, 1995) to document the epistemic functions of each utterance in the three focal discussions. In general, IA involves making inferences about “knowledge in use” that are grounded in the visible and audible traces of interactants’ utterances (Hall & Stevens, 2015). In our case, we were interested in making inferences from teacher and student utterances about knowledge in use as it concerned idea work. This form of analysis is in line with previous work (e.g. Elby, 2001; Hutchison & Hammer, 2010) that detailed the epistemic criteria in the substance of classroom talk. In our study, we documented the epistemic function in the substance of teacher and student utterances during each discussion.

Finally, to make larger claims about idea work, we drew on Robertson, Richards, and Elby’s (2015) notion of “attentional coherences.” They mobilized this analytic construct to describe how fine-grained shifts in teacher attention were embedded within coarser-grained, temporally-bound attentional coherences. We adapted this idea to characterize how the epistemic functions of utterances were embedded in coarser-grained conversational segments related to the idea work in each discussion. In turn, the character and pattern of these segments within and across the discussion were used to construct epistemic themes concerning the community’s collective sensemaking in different discussion types.

Analytic flow. To begin, the first two authors went through multiple, iterative rounds of coding for the epistemic function of each classroom utterance in the three focal discussions. In

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each round, the first and second author began by independently coding the transcript for epistemic function. We coded epistemic function by utterance instead of turn to capture the full range of idea work being done because one turn could serve multiple different epistemic functions (asking for clarification of an idea and inviting others into the discussion, for example). After independently coding, we met together to share our codes, discuss areas of agreement and disagreement, resolve any differences, and modify our coding scheme based on what we saw, using a grounded, iterative approach (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). We then repeated this process until we were at complete agreement on the codes and coding. This process took between three and five rounds for each discussion. Table 3 shows our final list of epistemic function codes with representative examples.

Table 3*Epistemic Function Codes*

Code	Description	Example
<i>Proposing an idea</i>	A speaker in the classroom community proposes an idea in and for discussion.	"First of all the people saying she was dehydrated, we should do a urine test."
<i>Probing an idea</i>	A speaker requests and/or pushes for clarification on an idea that is currently in discussion.	"Heart beat? And do we know how they do that? Does the doctor, I mean have you ever had your heart beat checked?"
<i>Clarifying an idea</i>	A speaker adds more information about an idea without modifying the substance of that original idea or incorporating evidence from investigations or past lesson experiences.	"There's one where you blow into a tube that I've done before. Where they see how much pressure you can breathe out."
<i>Restating an idea</i>	A speaker asks for or repeats a previously stated idea verbally or in writing for the public record in the classroom.	<i>Teacher:</i> "Check her?" <i>Student:</i> "Breathing pattern" <i>Teacher:</i> "Check breathing patterns"
<i>Redirecting an idea</i>	A speaker takes an idea that is being discussed dyadically and redirects it to the whole group to consider and discuss.	"anyone have any idea how we could check that?" "has anyone ever done that before?"
<i>Building on an idea</i>	A speaker adds more information about an idea using evidence from an investigation or lesson experience. In so doing, they may modify the substance of the original idea.	"The smoke is the molecules going up, that's why the mass reduces and equals the smoke "

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Code	Description	Example
<i>Connecting to previous or future ideas</i>	A speaker connects the ideas in the discussion to things that had been discussed in earlier lessons or things they would be doing in the future. These previous and future connections are not in discussion at the the time of the utterance.	"We spent yesterday, you guys, a long time about saying exploring her digestive system, and being able to compare it to a healthy person"
<i>Framing the ideas to be explored</i>	A speaker frames the goal(s) of the discussion or posits the broader question they are trying to make sense of <u>OR</u> discusses how they will attempt to reach that goal during the discussion	"I think what we want to ... make sure we include information that will successfully help us create a model that answers how does a healthy digestive system work and then how is McKenna's working differently than that"
<i>Evaluating an idea</i>	The speaker evaluates an idea that is being discussed for the public record. This evaluation can be can be explicitly stated or implicitly implied based on the tone of the utterance and context of the situation. It may also mediate whether an idea will be accepted or rejected from the public record.	"I didn't get that. That's brilliant." "Ah↑, there's holes in the small..."
<i>Eliciting ideas</i>	The speaker explicitly or implicitly asks for more ideas to be shared in discussion.	"So, any final burning pieces of information you feel need to be added?" "That's it? We should end the conference?"
<i>No epistemic function</i>	An utterance from a speaker that does not serve an epistemic function regarding any scientific ideas.	"Would you take that piece and put it up over here so that we have more room. I borrowed this from Ms. M's class."

After completing the epistemic function analysis, the first two authors collaboratively analyzed the patterns of epistemic functions to inductively uncover the broader conversational segments (Robertson et al., 2015). These conversational segments represented distinct patterns of idea work within and across each discussion. The conversational segments we found fell into four categories: surfacing and clarifying ideas, building an idea, evaluating an idea, and positioning the discussion. Surfacing and clarifying ideas was when the primary work being done by the discussion was generating a list of ideas related to the goal of the discussion and clarifying what exactly those proposed ideas were. Building an idea took place when evidence from investigations or classroom experiences were used to modify an idea that had been proposed. We

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found this distinct from clarifying because the idea itself changed based on the incorporation of new evidence. Evaluating an idea would occur when an idea was evaluated for its utility towards achieving the goal of the discussion. Finally, positioning the discussion occurred when the teacher explained how the discussion built from or would connect to other activities in the curriculum.

After identifying these conversational segments, we constructed epistemic themes based on the patterns of these segments within and across each discussion. These epistemic themes summarized the durable forms of idea work within and across each discussion and also highlighted specific moves and interactive patterns that supported or inhibited students' collective sensemaking.

Results

Based on our turn-taking analysis, we constructed one interactional theme: *teacher-student dyad was the most common interactional pattern across all discussions*. Our idea work analysis revealed consistencies and variation across Mr. Morse's implementation of the three discussion types. We found that across all discussions, Mr. Morse focused on surfacing and clarifying the students' ideas about the topic, which led to our first epistemic theme: that *surfacing and clarifying ideas occurred across all discussion types*. On the other hand, we saw much more variation in his implementation of building and evaluating ideas, which led to our second epistemic theme: that *building and evaluating ideas varied in prevalence and effectiveness across the discussions*.

Interactive Theme: Teacher-Student Dyad Across Discussions

We began our turn taking analysis by counting the number of turns taken by students and the teacher in each discussion. During the consensus discussion, Mr. Morse designated one

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student as the facilitator of the discussion. As we discussed in the methods, this student facilitator's role was substantially different from the other students', so we tracked her separately to better reveal patterns in turn taking in the discussion. Across all three discussions, non-facilitator students spoke for about half of the turns, as shown by Figure 2. In both the initial ideas and building understandings discussion, Mr. Morse spoke for close to 50% of the turns. In the consensus discussion, he spoke for 38% of the turns, but when his turns are considered in conjunction with the student facilitator, they together also took about half of the turns. This consistency across the three discussions suggests that the teacher remained a relatively central player in all three discussions and his degree of speaking did not vary greatly across discussion types.

Figure 2

Turns Taken by Role Across Discussions

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Although percent of turns taken provides a rough estimate of the level of interaction of the teacher and students, it does not provide information about the types of interactions that took place. Therefore, we analyzed each interaction based on the number of turns taken by one or more students between each teacher turn. We counted the number of dyadic teacher-student interactions (coded as TS) and interactions with multiple student turns between teacher turns. For example, a pattern that involved two student turns between the teacher (teacher-student-student), would be coded as TSS. As shown in Table 4, the most common interaction pattern by far was dyadic, teacher-student. The initial ideas and building understandings discussions each had only one instance of multiple students speaking between teacher turns. The consensus discussion showed a more complex set of interaction patterns because of the use of a student facilitator (F). Nevertheless, there were only two instances of multiple non-facilitator students contributing between teacher or facilitator turns.

Table 4

Counts of Interaction Patterns Across Discussions

Interaction Pattern	Initial Ideas	Building Understandings	Consensus
TS (FS)	36	16	39 / 18
TSS (FSS)	1		0 / 1
TSSS		1	
TSSSSS			1
TF			4
TFS			5

The consensus discussion was more interactionally complex than the other two discussions because of the presence of a student facilitator, whom we call Kayla. We found,

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however, that Kayla almost exclusively took over traffic directing interactions from Mr. Morse, such as calling on students to speak and ensuring the public record of ideas was maintained. An example of an interaction between Kayla, Mr. Morse, and another student in Table 5 demonstrates these roles.

Table 5

Transcript from Consensus Discussion

1	Kayla	Nathan
2	Nathan	Molecules don't just disappear
3	Mr. Morse	So why do you want to include that?
4	Nathan	Um, because it is important to note that the molecules go somewhere cause it just doesn't disappear.
5	Mr. Morse	So our model should show that they're not just disappearing. Our model should show them going somewhere, right?
6	Nathan	Yes.
7	Kayla	Ashley [calling on a different student]

Here, Kayla took on the traffic directing role by inviting Nathan to talk during turn 1. She then yielded the floor to Nathan and Mr. Morse to have a more substantive dyadic interaction about the idea of molecules disappearing in turns 2 through 6, until she took over the traffic directing by calling on a different student in turn 7. The fact that Kayla was a student serving in the traffic directing role traditionally taken on by the teacher potentially communicated Mr. Morse's trust in his students' abilities to direct their own conversations. Nevertheless, it did not lead to substantially more meaningful student-to-student interaction than seen in the other discussions.

Overall, the turn-taking analysis supports the idea that Mr. Morse acted as a central speaker throughout all three discussions and facilitated student contribution mostly through

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dyadic interactions between him and individual students. This interaction pattern persisted across all three discussions despite the different goals of each discussion. For example, the purpose of the consensus discussion quoted in Table 5 was for students to consolidate their understanding of multiple pieces of an idea and build a joint agreement on how they could make sense of the phenomenon of interest (M’Kenna’s symptoms). This type of collective sensemaking was particularly challenging to achieve purely through dyadic teacher-student interaction.

Epistemic Theme 1: Surfacing & Clarifying Ideas Occurred in Each Discussion Type

Figure 3 maps the discussion segments we identified across all three discussions. Each discussion is represented by a horizontal line with the conversational segments separated by vertical lines. Numbers are included to show the utterances that fell within each segment; for example, in the initial ideas discussion, the first 80 utterances were part of the surfacing and clarifying ideas segment and utterances 81-89 were spent positioning the discussion. The maps reveal two main patterns across the discussions: the absence of evaluation (E) and the presence of surfacing and clarifying (S). Mr. Morse dedicated substantial time to the surfacing and clarifying ideas in each discussion type: 90% of the utterances in the initial ideas discussion, 20% of the utterances during the building understandings discussion, and 62% of the utterances during the consensus discussion.

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Figure 3*Conversational Segments of Focal Discussions**Initial ideas:*

Key:

S: Surfacing & clarifying ideas

E: Evaluating an idea

B: Building an idea

P: Positioning the discussion

Note: Each utterance in each discussion was numbered sequentially. Numbers in parentheses show which utterances made up each conversational segment.

As discussed in the previous section, the primary interactional pattern across all three discussions was teacher-student dyad. Therefore, the most common combination of epistemic and interactional pattern across all three discussions was surfacing and clarifying ideas in teacher-student dyad. Within these segments, we identified a characteristic talk pattern we termed the Propose-Probe-Clarify-Restate (PPCR) sequence. In this sequence, a student proposed an idea, Mr. Morse then probed that idea further, and the student responded by clarifying what he or she initially meant. After one or more rounds of probing and clarifying, the

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idea was restated usually while being written on a poster to be accepted into the public record of the discussion.

Table 6 shows an example of this PPCR sequence. In this initial ideas discussion, Mr. Morse had asked the class, “What are some proposed investigations we could have?...Anything else we might want to check? You’re the healthcare provider, right? Then you need to figure this out for M’Kenna.” In the first turn of the exchange shown in Table 6, Andy suggested that they “Check BMI” to help them figure out what was wrong with M’Kenna. In turns 2, 4, and 6, Mr. Morse probed Andy’s idea to understand what he meant by BMI and why he thought it may be important to understand M’Kenna’s case. Finally, in turn 8, he accepted the idea and wrote it on the “ideas for investigation” chart posted on the wall. This repeated sequence of teacher surfacing and clarifying moves illustrates Mr. Morse’s commitment to publicly acknowledge and accept students’ ideas while also pushing them to further deepen and clarify those ideas.

Table 6

Example of a PPCR Sequence from the Initial Ideas Discussion

Transcript		Code
1	Andy: Check BMI	Propose
2	Mr. Morse: BMI, what do you mean by that	Probe
3	Andy: Body Mass Index	Clarify
4	Mr. Morse: What is that?	Probe
5	Andy: Their height and weight	Clarify
6	Mr. Morse: What does that tell you?	Probe
7	Andy: If you are underweight or overweight	Clarify
8	Mr. Morse: So BMI, which is what?	Restate
9	Andy: Body Mass Index	Restate

The PPCR sequence took place in every discussion observed and was a characteristic indicator of surfacing and clarifying ideas in Mr. Morse’s classroom. We identified five distinct

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repetitions of this sequence in both the initial ideas and consensus discussion and one example in the building understandings discussion, demonstrating the time and care that Mr. Morse took in ensuring his students' ideas were heard and understood by the class.

Overall, engagement in surfacing and clarifying ideas was necessary for all three types of discussions to make visible students different ideas. In the initial ideas discussion, this work helped to accomplish the goals of this discussion: to get students' initial ideas and experiences on the table in language that was accessible to the classroom community, such as the clarification of BMI. In the discussion, nine distinct ideas were quickly generated by the class, but because of the teacher-dominated PPCR sequences, students only interacted with Mr. Morse to clarify their ideas, rather than with each other. Therefore, surfacing and clarifying ideas through dyadic PPCR sequences did not effectively interanimate (Scott et al., 2006) students' ideas.

Surfacing and clarifying ideas was also necessary for the building understandings and consensus discussions to provide ideas for the class to work with. The prevalence of this segment across all three discussions illustrated the time and care that Mr. Morse took to surface and understand multiple students' ideas. His attention to his students' ideas likely communicated that he found their thinking important and valuable. However, the extensive time he spent on this surfacing work in these two discussions may have ultimately hindered time spent on the other epistemic goals of the discussions.

Epistemic Theme 2: Building & Evaluating Ideas Varied in Prevalence and Effectiveness Across the Discussions

In general, we observed significantly less building and evaluating ideas across all three discussions. This pattern is particularly problematic for consensus and building understandings discussions, which require ideas to be constructed and critiqued using evidence (Ford, 2012;

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Windschitl et al., 2018). Across these two discussions, we also observed a difference in the quality and quantity of epistemic work related to the building and evaluation of ideas.

Building Understandings Discussion

Mr. Morse's implementation of the building understandings discussion demonstrated the most successful collective sensemaking and best alignment with the goals of the discussion type. The discussion took place after the students had completed an investigation tracking changes in mass after various types of food were burned. The goal of this discussion was for students to jointly establish the idea that burning is a chemical reaction that releases a gas, as evidenced by the drop in mass of the item being burned. During the discussion, Mr. Morse facilitated some surfacing of ideas, but it was a relatively smaller portion of the discussion as compared to the other two discussions observed (20% of utterances). For much of the discussion, the class worked on building a specific idea that burning is a chemical reaction that involves a state change using evidence from the investigation. In total, 80% of the utterances in this discussion were dedicated to building ideas in either dyadic or class-wide discussion (see figure 4).

Figure 4*Detailed Map of Building Understandings Discussion**Building understandings:*

Key:

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------|
| S1: Surfacing & clarifying ideas through teacher-student dyad | P: Positioning the discussion |
| S2: Surfacing & clarifying ideas through class-wide discussion | E: Evaluating an idea |
| B1: Building an idea through teacher-student dyad | |
| B2: Building an idea through class-wide discussion | |

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These building segments contained some of Mr. Morse's most effective and varied facilitation moves. For example, in one sequence, Mr. Morse probed a student's idea to clarify whether or not a chemical change occurred when fuel was burned in the previous investigations. Following a series of probes from Mr. Morse, he then redirected the discussion to the rest of the class. This exchange is found in Table 7.

Table 7

Transcript from Building Understandings Discussion

	Transcript	Code
1	Mr. Morse: How many people think it's still wood after it burns?	Redirect
2	Katrina: Just a different form, not form but	Restate
3	Izzy: A different state.	Clarify
4	Katrina: Yeah state.	Eval.
5	Mr. Morse: Oh a different state, from solid to liquid, liquid to gas?	Restate Clarify
6	Katrina: Yeah, thank you.	Eval.
7	Mr. Morse: So the wood became a gas?	Probe
8	Katrina: No, it became something else.	Clarify
9	Mr. Morse: Oh it became something else. Rochelle, what do you think about that?	Restate Elicit
10	Rochelle: I think it changed into a different substance.	Build
11	Mr. Morse: Do we have a term for when a substance changes into a different substance?	Probe
12	Juan: A chemical reaction.	Clarify
13	Mr. Morse: A chemical reaction	Restate

Mr. Morse began this excerpt by redirecting to the entire group at turn 1, asking "how many people think it's still wood after it burns?" This move positioned the rest of the class to grapple with the conceptual tension raised by Katrina in turns 2, 4, and 8 that wood could react but still remain wood. In turn 10, Rochelle built further on Katrina's idea of "it became something else" suggesting that it "changed into a different substance." Finally, in turn 12 Juan further clarified

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that this could have occurred during “a chemical reaction.” This interaction differs from the surfacing and clarifying example in Table 6 because the students are adding more information to Katrina’s initial idea, resulting in the idea changing across this interaction from a change in state (turn 4) to a chemical reaction (turn 12).

This excerpt also demonstrates multiple moves Mr. Morse made to encourage his students to interanimate (Bakhtin, 1981), build on, and evaluate each other’s ideas. First, he avoided direct evaluation of his students’ responses, opening up opportunities for students to evaluate each other’s ideas, such as in turn 11 when Rochelle addressed Katrina’s original idea; avoiding evaluative statements like this can help to open up student talk in the classroom (Nassaji & Wells, 2000). Second, when Mr. Morse probed his students’ ideas, his moves focused primarily on asking for evidence and for students’ deeper reasoning. For example, in turns 7 and 12, he was pushing his students to think more critically about their own ideas rather than simply clarify a term they had used, which can support complex evidence building work (Manz & Renga, 2017). These choices potentially contributed to the increased interanimation and building of ideas we observed in that discussion compared to the other two.

Consensus Discussion

In comparison to the building understandings discussion, Mr. Morse’s enactment of the consensus discussion was less aligned to the underlying epistemic goals of this discussion type. The plurality of the utterances (44%) in the consensus discussion involved surfacing and clarifying ideas. This surfacing work is necessary for the development of a list of ideas for inclusion in the consensus model. However, as we discussed in the introduction, consensus discussions require further work on the ideas that are generated and necessitate the synthesis and evaluation of ideas drawn from multiple lessons across time (Windschitl et al., 2018). The fact

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that Mr. Morse dedicated the majority of the utterances to surfacing ideas made it difficult to achieve that goal in enactment.

Figure 5 is a detailed map of the consensus discussion Mr. Morse facilitated, which shows that the class spent much of its time surfacing and clarifying ideas but rarely built or evaluated them. Only 30% of the utterances were spent building ideas using evidence and no segments of the discussion focused on evaluating ideas for their alignment with that evidence or relevance to the consensus model.

Figure 5*Detailed Map of Consensus Discussion*

Key:

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------|
| S1: Surfacing & clarifying ideas through teacher-student dyad | P: Positioning the discussion |
| S2: Surfacing & clarifying ideas through class-wide discussion | E: Evaluating an idea |
| B1: Building an idea through teacher-student dyad | |
| B2: Building an idea through class-wide discussion | |

In the building segments, two ideas were constructed using evidence from past investigations and lessons prior to their inclusion in the public record. As with the building ideas segment in the building understandings discussion, the key feature during the consensus discussion was the use of evidence to modify and support the ideas as they were being worked on, rather than simply clarifying or adding scientific vocabulary. The consensus discussion was different in that the evidence came from past investigations and lessons instead of the existing one. In one dyadic segment shown in Table 8, for example, Mr. Morse pushed Veronica to provide evidence from previous lessons' findings and experiences before allowing the inclusion of her idea in the public record.

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Table 8*Transcript from Consensus Discussion*

Transcript		Code
1	Mr. Morse: Okay. Do we have evidence that fiber and water are excreted?	Probe
2	Veronica: Um --yeah	Build
3	Mr. Morse: What was the evidence?	Probe
4	Veronica: There was like a dye that you injected that later on the data was like a pie circle and how much water there is, how much fiber there is, and like other molecules.	Build
5	Mr. Morse: In -- in what?	Probe
6	Veronica: In the waste.	Clarify
7	Mr. Morse: And what about absorption?	Probe
8	Veronica: Protein are like how an example of how glucose gets absorbed and be in like the small intestine	Clarify
9	Mr. Morse: We have evidence for that right? That glucose gets the --what was the evidence for that?	Probe
10	Veronica: The experiment.	Build
11	Mr. Morse: Which experiment?	Probe
12	Veronica: The dialysis tube.	Clarify
13	Mr. Morse: Yep. Do we have evidence that amino acids and fatty acids are absorbed?	Probe
14	Veronica: Um-I'm not-I think so.	Build

This exchange began with Mr. Morse asking Veronica for evidence that fiber was excreted in waste. Veronica provided that evidence in turns 4 and 6 and then in turn 8 further proposed that proteins and glucose are absorbed in the small intestine. After Mr. Morse pushed her for evidence of that in turns 9, 11, and 13, Veronica states in turn 14 that she did not yet have evidence to support her claim that amino acids and proteins are absorbed by the small intestine. This idea building resembled the type of epistemic work in the building understandings discussion in that they both involved the construction of ideas using evidence. However, unlike the building understandings discussion, this evidence did not come from the current lesson investigation, but rather from multiple previous lesson investigations. As a result, the building

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work in the consensus discussion involved *rebuilding* previously constructed lesson ideas rather than the building of new ideas from the results of a current lesson investigation.

In this example Veronica, rebuilt an idea using evidence. However, Mr. Morse did not redirect her idea to the class for it to be evaluated for either evidentiary heft or relevance to the anchoring phenomenon. In addition, once this idea was built and accepted, Mr. Morse returned to a set of PPCR sequences similar to the initial ideas discussion. As a result, the students' ideas were not interanimated but simply built and written down. In fact, the majority of the utterances—101 out of 164—were spent surfacing and clarifying ideas (see Figure 5), demonstrating how Mr. Morse's facilitation of the consensus and initial ideas discussions were similar.

Overall, we found that Mr. Morse's class engaged variably in the building and evaluating of ideas in the three discussions. For the initial ideas discussion, the absence of the construction and evaluation of ideas was largely to be expected as this was not the goal of this discussion. For the building understandings discussion, the class engaged in productive dyadic and class-wide exchanges concerning the construction of ideas using evidence from that lesson. This epistemic work was supported by Mr. Morse's instructional moves (e.g. probing for deeper reasoning) in enactment. Lastly, for the consensus discussion, the rebuilding of some ideas using evidence did allow for greater conceptual rigor in the ideas included in the public record, but this epistemic work was engaged in sparingly by the class. Instead, the prevalence of PPCR sequences marked a focus on surfacing and clarifying ideas at the expense of class-wide evaluation of those ideas. This emphasis limited the collective sensemaking possible for the discussion.

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Discussion

In this study, we investigated how idea work and interactional patterns varied across three different types of discussion—initial ideas, building understandings, and consensus—and how teacher moves shaped the class’s collective sensemaking. These discussion types are a useful frame to analyze both interaction and idea work in classroom discussions. Past work has outlined possible goals for discussions but have not used those goals to look at how teachers facilitate discussions (e.g. Michaels & O’Connor, 2012). Alternatively, other studies have focused on specific aspects of science learning such as conducting investigations and found that different kinds of work elicit distinctive talk patterns (Manz & Renga, 2017; Rees & Roth, 2017). We have shown that the discussion types framework can capture the range of discussion goals likely in a storyline unit.

In this section, we discuss three key takeaways from our analysis. First, we emphasize the importance of surfacing and clarifying ideas as a step in collective sensemaking that comes before the construction and critique of those ideas (Ford, 2012). Second, we highlight the Propose-Probe-Clarify-Restate (PPCR) sequence and its affordances in helping students to surface and clarify ideas. Finally, we discuss how each discussion type requires a different set of teacher moves to achieve their goal and show how surfacing and clarifying of ideas is necessary but insufficient to support sensemaking in all discussion types.

Surfacing and clarifying ideas to support collective sensemaking

Across each discussion, Mr. Morse consistently engaged his class in surfacing and clarifying ideas, opening up each discussion for students to share their thoughts and perspectives. This surfacing of ideas and experiences creates space for students to safely and equitably participate in collaborative sensemaking (Bang et al., 2012; Hand, 2012). Encouraging students

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to verbalize their scientific thinking and valuing the substance of their ideas (rather than the memorization of predetermined scientific definitions) can support a sense of belonging for students who typically do not identify with science (Lemmi et al., 2019).

In general, candidate ideas need to be surfaced and clarified for the classroom community prior to engagement in more systematic forms of construction and critique (Harris et al., 2012). Previous authors have used multiple metaphors to describe this surfacing of ideas, including “setting the table” (Michaels & O’Connor, 2012) or going “shopping” for ideas (Hammer & van Zee, 2006), which involves the class publicly considering the relevance of ideas for figuring out a phenomenon (Kapon, 2017). It is important that the classroom community do this surfacing work to ensure that the ideas addressed later in the sensemaking process are authentically “theirs” and not directed solely by the teacher or curriculum (Sikorski & Hammer, 2017). Therefore, we argue that authentic engagement in construction and critique of ideas (Ford, 2012), is emergent from and intertwined with the surfacing and clarifying of ideas.

Affordances of the Propose-Probe-Clarify-Restate Sequence

Past work has shown that the canonical IRE talk sequence can be more complex than initially thought and support multiple types of idea work in the classroom (Nassaji & Wells, 2000; Rees & Roth, 2019; Wells & Mejia Arauz, 2006). Scholars have identified a range of talk patterns that build on IRE, such as I-R-F-R-F- and I-R-Q-R-A (Mortimer & Scott, 2003; Rees & Roth, 2019). Building on this past work in identifying talk patterns, we have identified and characterized a novel talk pattern that is characteristic of surfacing and clarifying ideas: the propose-probe-clarify-estate (PPCR) sequence.

The PPCR sequence is similar to previously defined talk patterns such as the I-R-F-R-F- sequence (Mortimer & Scott, 2003) in that it involves students building on repeated questions

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from the teacher. In addition, it involves the teacher sticking with the same student over multiple turns, which can communicate that the teacher values their students' thinking rather than simply looking for a correct answer (Affolter, 2020). What makes PPCR distinct from previously identified talk patterns is the teacher's use of clarifying and restating. These talk moves help to honor and acknowledge the ideas students bring to a discussion and restate them to ensure they are accepted into a public record of the discussion (Michaels & O'Connor, 2015). Therefore, we found the PPCR sequence to be a powerful vehicle to surface ideas quickly, to position students' ideas as valuable for public consideration, and to support the development of an equitable classroom community in which all students' ideas were important.

Discussion Types Require Different Teacher Moves

While the PPCR sequence was a powerful way for Mr. Morse to surface and clarify his students' ideas, we found that he relied on this same set of moves in each discussion. Given the different goals of the three discussion types, teachers have different responsibilities in facilitating the surfacing of ideas in each type of discussion. During initial ideas discussions, the primary goal is for students to share their ideas and experiences related to the topic; therefore, the teacher does not need to be concerned with foregrounding specific ideas for public shopping and subsequent work. Nevertheless, even an initial ideas discussion should include some sort of agreement on next steps, which means ideas can benefit from being interanimated and built rather than simply listed and clarified.

Unlike initial ideas discussions, consensus and building understandings discussions require particular lesson-specific ideas to be surfaced and foregrounded to support the development of students' disciplinary understanding (Maskiewicz & Winters, 2012; Russ et al., 2009). Therefore, the teacher must facilitate dialogic but targeted surfacing of ideas so that the

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group can own and work with them later in the discussion. This means that while the PPCR sequence may be a helpful tool to begin those discussions, it is insufficient to achieve the goals of consensus and building understanding discussions.

During the consensus discussion, we found that Mr. Morse relied heavily on the PPCR sequence and as a result did not push students to build and evaluate ideas across time to make sense of a phenomenon. Instead, most of the discussion was spent surfacing and clarifying ideas with some time dedicated to rebuilding ideas students had made sense of earlier in the unit (see Figure 5). Mr. Morse rarely used evaluation moves during the consensus discussion and never explicitly facilitated the capture of areas of agreement or disagreement in students' understanding. As a result, Mr. Morse facilitated the development of a list of student ideas that were under-evaluated by the classroom community.

In contrast, during the building understandings discussion Mr. Morse spent a short time surfacing and clarifying ideas and then quickly moved on to building an idea (see Figure 4). He did so by switching from the PPCR pattern to other instructional moves such as redirecting ideas to the whole group (Michaels & O'Connor, 2012), evaluating ideas for evidence, and asking direct questions concerning evidence (Manz & Renga, 2017). As a result, students were able to work together to effectively make sense of their investigation to come to a greater understanding of how chemical reactions take place in the body.

Taken together, therefore, these three discussions show how surfacing and clarifying ideas, and the PPCR sequence that marks that work, is necessary but insufficient for supporting collaborative student sensemaking. While all three discussion types require ideas to be initially surfaced for public consideration (Hammer & van Zee, 2006; Michaels & O'Connor, 2012), the subsequent moves should be different. Initial ideas discussions should include some comparing

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of ideas to determine the class's next steps, building understandings require target ideas to be built using evidence from the lesson, and consensus discussions require ideas from previous lessons to be rebuilt and evaluated for relevance in explaining the phenomenon of interest.

Limitations and Implications

While we have been able to dive deeply into the discussion work that took place in the implementation of this storyline unit, we also acknowledge that the generalizability and transferability of claims from this study are inherently limited by the nature of a single case study. The goal of single case study methodology is not to create general claims but rather to develop deep explanations of a particular event or phenomenon (Yin, 2018). As a result, we recommend that much more research be done to understand how the discussion types framework can help analysis and implementation of class discussions and how idea work can vary across discussion types.

Implications for Design of Professional Learning and Curriculum

We see valuable implications from this study in terms of how we might support teachers in facilitating discussions in their classroom. Because Mr. Morse did not consider how each discussion might have had distinct goals, he might have benefitted from explicit professional learning around the discussion types and how to move beyond the teacher-student dyad. Teachers are used to dyadic interactional patterns in the classroom (Lemke, 1990; Mortimer & Scott, 2003), but our results suggest that those patterns might constrain the idea work that can take place, supporting surfacing and clarifying ideas more than building or evaluating them. Highlighting teacher moves that help students to interanimate and critique ideas could support teachers in this challenging shift in classroom discourse.

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For example, Mr. Morse may have benefited from using vignettes or classroom video to observe and reflect on the role of redirecting moves like, *How many other people had a similar idea?* or evaluating ones like, *I am hearing (Idea X) and (Idea Y). Do we have evidence that challenges one of these ideas?* Professional development has been shown to have the potential to expand teachers' instructional repertoire in general (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2015; Wilson, 2013) and around the facilitation of classroom discussion specifically (Chen et al., 2020). Future research should investigate how the discussion types framework may be used to expand that repertoire during professional development.

Even if it were not feasible for Mr. Morse to attend professional development, the curricular materials could have been better written to emphasize the goals of these discussions. This use of educative curricular materials is one strategy for supporting teacher learning (Davis & Krajcik, 2005), and strong educative supports inform teachers about the *what*, *how*, and *why* of instructional activity as designed in the curriculum (Bismack et al., 2015). In order for teachers to effectively use discussions to support collective sensemaking, they must better understand *what* epistemic work goes into collective sensemaking in each discussion, *how* this work can be facilitated by the teacher, and *why* it is important for supporting student learning.

Our study has clarified some of this *what*, *how*, and *why* by showing, for example, the importance of building and evaluating ideas rather than focusing solely on surfacing them, especially in building understandings and consensus discussions. Future curriculum materials would benefit from supports that make these ideas explicit for teachers as they attempt to facilitate collective sensemaking through class discussion. We believe that if teachers have access to curricular materials designed to effectively use discussions of various types, experiences that help them understand the discussion types, and practice with interactional

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patterns that allow for complex building and evaluating work, we may see strong benefits in supporting students' collective sensemaking.

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